

Additional File 2. Further results for correlations found in susceptibility test results from wild vector populations

Figure S2. The distributions of paired pyrethroid susceptibility test mortality values for *An. gambiae* s.l. Each point represents the results from a single *An. gambiae* s.l. sample that was subdivided between susceptibility tests for two different pyrethroids to give a pair of percent mortality values.

Figure S3. The distributions of paired pyrethroid susceptibility test mortality values for the *An. funestus* subgroup.

Figure S4. The distributions of paired pyrethroid susceptibility test mortality values for four species.

Each point represents the results for a single species from a mosquito sample that was subdivided between susceptibility tests for two different pyrethroids to give a pair of percent mortality values.

Figure S5. The distributions of paired susceptibility test mortality values for four species exposed to deltamethrin and a non-pyrethroid insecticide. Each point represents the results for a single species from a mosquito sample that was subdivided between two susceptibility tests for deltamethrin and a non-pyrethroid insecticide to give a pair of percent mortality values.

Table S4. Correlations between resistance to deltamethrin and non-pyrethroid insecticides in four African malaria vector species

Deltamethrin vs DDT	N	Correlation
<i>Anopheles arabiensis</i>	107	0.808*
<i>Anopheles coluzzii</i>	69	0.506*
<i>Anopheles coluzzii/gambiae</i>	62	0.545*
<i>Anopheles gambiae</i>	43	0.370 ^{n.s.}
<i>Anopheles funestus</i>	48	-0.071 ^{n.s.}
Deltamethrin vs bendiocarb		
<i>Anopheles arabiensis</i>	97	-0.224 ^{n.s.}
<i>Anopheles coluzzii</i>	22	0.133 ^{n.s.}
<i>Anopheles coluzzii/gambiae</i>	28	0.218 ^{n.s.}
<i>Anopheles gambiae</i>	22	0.073 ^{n.s.}
<i>Anopheles funestus</i>	35	0.439 ^{n.s.}
Deltamethrin vs fenitrothion		
<i>Anopheles arabiensis</i>	55	0.170 ^{n.s.}
Deltamethrin vs malathion		
<i>Anopheles arabiensis</i>	37	0.084 ^{n.s.}
<i>Anopheles funestus</i>	29	0.061 ^{n.s.}
Deltamethrin vs pirimiphos-methyl		
<i>Anopheles arabiensis</i>	34	0.246 ^{n.s.}
Deltamethrin vs propoxur		
<i>Anopheles arabiensis</i>	34	0.249 ^{n.s.}

Significant results (at the 0.05 level with a Holm-Bonferroni correction) are denoted by *. The term ‘*Anopheles coluzzii/gambiae*’ refers to mosquito samples that were undifferentiated between *An. coluzzii* and *An. gambiae*, or M and S forms, before they were recognised as two species. Non-significant results are denoted n.s.

Figure S6. Comparisons between resistance to etofenprox and five other pyrethroids, measured using standard WHO susceptibility tests in (A) the *An. gambiae* complex and (B) the *An. funestus* subgroup.

Significant (at the 0.05 level with a Holm-Bonferroni correction) results from a paired-sample t-test are denoted ‘sig.’, non-significant results are denoted ‘n.s.’, and ‘n’ is the number of pairs in each set.

Deltamethrin vs Permethrin Resistance in Malaria Vector Complexes

Deltamethrin vs λ -Cyhalothrin Resistance in Malaria Vector Complexes

Permethrin vs λ -Cyhalothrin Resistance in Malaria Vector Complexes

Figure S7. Comparison of resistance to three pyrethroids in the *An. gambiae* complex and *An. funestus* subgroup. Significant results (at the 0.05 level with a Holm-Bonferroni correction) from a paired-sample t-test are denoted 'sig.', non-significant results are denoted 'n.s.', and 'n' is the number of pairs in each set.

Deltamethrin vs Permethrin Resistance in Malaria Vector Species

Deltamethrin vs λ -Cyhalothrin Resistance in Malaria Vector Species

Permethrin vs λ -Cyhalothrin Resistance in Malaria Vector Species

Figure S8. Comparison of resistance to three pyrethroids in four malaria vector species. Two species, *An. coluzzii* and *An. gambiae*, were previously classified as one and results for this former species are entitled 'coluzzii/gambiae'. Significant results (at the 0.05 level with a Holm-Bonferroni correction) from a paired-sample t-test are denoted 'sig.', non-significant results are denoted 'n.s.', and 'n' is the number of pairs in each set.

Figure S9. Comparison of resistance to deltamethrin and six insecticides from other classes. Two species, *An. coluzzii* and *An. gambiae*, were previously classified as one and results for this former species are entitled '*coluzzii/gambiae*'. Significant results (at the 0.05 level with a Holm-Bonferroni correction) from a paired-sample t-test are denoted 'sig.', non-significant results are denoted 'n.s.', and 'n' is the number of pairs in each set.